

Challenges of Using e-learning Resources for Quality Education Delivery in Post COVID19: A Case Study of Secondary Schools in Zamfara State

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ABSTRACT

The paper explained challenges associated with the used of e-learning resources in delivering quality education in post covid period. This is so because e-learning. gives an opportunity to the learner to complete his/her education/sessions easily and conveniently. It is a very flexible and self-paced method of education. The secondary school layer of education was receiving its first major encounter with e-learning as a sole means of instructing the students especially during total and partial lockdowns and as well at post-covid period. The Secondary Schools in Zamfara State also experimented this along with many Nigerian schools using such channels as Radio, TV and the internet and related remote learning strategies and as such the paper looked at the evidence of experiences of some teachers from five secondary schools within the state employing a qualitative approach. Three teachers were selected from each school (n=15) to elicit their responses on the three objectives. It was on this premises that, the paper identified and explained some major challenges that can hinder effective uses of these resources, such as E-learning Infrastructure; Quality of support systems, Quality of content and assessment; Peer support networks; E-learning. quality of the system that includes proper maintenance of software and hardware recourses; Skills gap in the initial training of teachers in e-learning uses among others. Recommendations were made that though avenues exist for successful development and practice of e-learning, improvement should be made on staff training, equipment, Internet connections to address the challenges raised.

Keywords: e-learning; Quality Education; Resources & Delivery

INTRODUCTION

The school closures in Nigeria caused considerable disruptions in the educational system, particularly in terms of learning styles and access to school-related services. School closures impacted about 40 million primary and secondary school students across Nigeria, including those in IDP camps. In response, the federal and state governments, as well as the private sector, implemented a variety of learning interventions employing technological platforms, internet-based tools,

and conventional media to mitigate the impact of learning disruption course by Covid-19. Hence, school closures due to COVID-19 coupled with insecurity has worsen educational development in Northwestern part of the country. The UNICEF reported that over 10.5 million children aged 5-14 years are out of school in Nigeria with about 70% of them coming from the North. Many federal and state government policies recognize the application of technology in education delivery, but not much for e-learning at basic

education level (Akogun et al., 2020). Over the years there has been a phenomenal growth in the use of e-learning resources for educational provisions at different levels but with the current addition to the health catastrophe of COVID-19 which has resulted in an educational crisis with 1.52 billion students missing school and related educational institutions. (Shehu, S. A; Usman, A. Y, Zilkamaini, A. M, & Safina, A. Y, 2021 & UNESCO, 2020).

Therefore, Countries have implemented some form of learning via electronic means (e-learning) and other form such as remote learning programmes which utilizes variety of technologies to assure learning continuity. However, this learning platform, has its own set of challenges to cope with, in order to ensure effective usage. Notable to all, learning is an active process of building knowledge and skills through practice within a supportive community. It comprises not only a process of continual personal development and enrichment, but also the possibility of rapid and radical conceptual change. Traditional, classroom context of learning typically occurs in a teacher-directed instructional context with face-to-face interaction in a live synchronous environment. But in contrast to this form of instruction, is an approach that promotes learner-directed learning where teaching and learning are no longer restricted to traditional classrooms, and this is possible with the with emerging internet commercialization and the expansion of information communication technologies (ICT), online or electronic learning (e-learning) environments offer the possibilities for communication, interaction and multimedia material delivery that enhance learner-directed learning. Hence, ICT has increasingly influenced educational provisions. (Shehu, S. A; Usman, A. Y, Zilkamaini, A. M, & Safina, A. Y, 2021 & UNESCO, 2020).

The pace at which technological inventions have been unfolding in recent history has shaped all spheres of the current socioeconomic reality and introduced new and greater demands on the socioeconomic actors and systems. Within the Education system in particular, these demands have catapulted the introduction and utilization of a number of technologies in terms of tools, media or resources alike. Academic inquiry has demonstrated how the entire elements of the education ecosystem draw on these inventions for the sustenance of the system and against its more improved performance. Teachers, students, administrators, parents and other education stakeholders have at various degrees been shown to rely on technology for Educational delivery, instruction, assessment and administration. Similarly, United Nation Education Scientific & Cultural Organization (UNESCO: 2004) asserts the crucial need to focus on the importance of lifelong learning and to upgrade knowledge and skills continuously, to think critically and to inspire creativity and innovation so as to adapt to global change. (Garland & Tadeja 2013).

In this trend of development, the Covid-19 pandemic which imposed global lockdowns and social distancing have represented the apex of global resort to technology for information mediation and delivery. Education here as well made remarkable utilization of technology tools, media and resources to a remarkable extent. Bello (2021) observed that the COVID-19 pandemic and its accompanying circumstances are one major world incident that has caused an unprecedented swift and dynamic turn toward a wider embrace of e-learning even in traditionally unusual educational quarters. This implies that though the Education system in Nigeria at the higher institutions level have long been used to e-learning deliveries, it is the incidence of

COVID 19 that ushered a period in which pre-tertiary Education in Nigeria have come to largely imbibe e-learning. Particularly, the Federal Ministry of Education in Nigeria in line with the global trend resorted to delivering learning content to pre-tertiary students through e-learning first by Educational radio and television and then by web. In culmination, the federal government eventually launched a dedicated website named inspire.education.gov.ng. By specifications, the website has at its launch in 2021 been adjudged to be the greatest open source national e-learning repertoire directed to secondary school teachers and learner's. over it contained 4,000 video lessons for elementary students, 7,000 video lessons for secondary students, and 4,000 audio lessons for secondary audience. The is in addition to many other e-learning platforms such as WAEC e-learning and so forth. (Bello, 2021).

The implementation of e-learning to a wide scale in pre-tertiary schooling particularly secondary schooling therefore represent a shift in teaching and learning paradigm in many African countries like Nigeria for a lot of teachers in the subsystem. These innovations were meant to improve access to advanced educational experiences by allowing students and teachers to participate in remote learning communities and to improve quality and effectiveness of education by supporting a collaborative learning process. Particularly, many developing countries trying expansion of technology to new areas are, however, faced with numerous challenges such as technical and organizational problems and the readiness of teachers and students are concerned (Andersson & Gronlund, 2009; Paschal & Mkulu 2020).

Educational development of this type in Nigeria are described as a challenging experience due to this newness. For many years, the educational system at the tertiary

level has internalized e-learning systems with the establishment of national open university of Nigeria, NOUN in the mid-2000s. Ever since the e-learning penetration has kept deepening even further. However, the secondary school teacher and student have largely been kept aloof from the development. Nigeria has a clear educational policy which hinged on the integration of the individual into a sound and effective citizen with equal educational opportunities to all Nigerians. In furtherance of this, Federal Government of Nigeria and some state governments established many means by which secondary school teachers and students can access e-learning resources and system and this becomes paramount for the fact that e-learning can occur through numerous types of media that deliver text, audio, images, animation, and streaming video, and includes technology applications and processes such as audio or video tape, satellite TV, CD-ROM, and computer-based learning. (Chibueze & Chukwuji 2021 & Vidyadeyi, 2014;).

Most of these resources are deliverable through the digitalization of formal school curriculum, in this case, the secondary schools. This is as it is established to support teaching and learning in the schools through provision of necessary facilities in quantities and qualities enough to achieve educational outcomes. Various studies have shown that most secondary have no specific elearning platform serving there teaches and students as obtains in tertiary schools (Fayomi Ayo, Ajayi & Okorie 2015) and that these schools do not have well equipped and functional libraries to serve needs of their teachers and students despite that many of these schools have qualified teachers. However research have also shown that that provision of open access to eLearning resources nearly replaces this

deficit (Chibueze & Chukwuji 2021; Sharifabadi 2006).

E-learning has largely been recognized as an important means to enhance the accessibility and improve quality of the teaching-learning process (Appana, 2008). It is viewed as a collection of tools, media and resources which provides opportunities for maximization and penetration of educational content to normal and disadvantaged students or those who are unable to attend classes due to physical, social or economic constraints (Vaughan, 2007). Other part of literature emphasizes the flexibility of e-learning in terms of elimination of space and time constraints. It was also shown to improve the quality of learning, prepare students better for a knowledge-based society, provides lifelong learning opportunities and supports critical thinking skills, problem-solving and so forth. Self-paced and real-time are two salient attributes of e-learning that warrant its adoption to large scale. ((Ersin & Atay 2021; Marshall, S. 2020; Moustakas & Robrade 2022; Yusuf & Al-Banawi 2013).

Thus the researchers acknowledged that e-learning was already in use before the pandemic and various challenges were associated with it but the sudden shift to it occasioned by the COVID-19 pandemic served to resurface and augment these challenges. For example, Aung & Khaing as cited in Moustakas & Robrade (2022) identified inadequate of technological resources, poor internet quality, and a lack of information communication technology (ICT) knowledge have been important barriers, especially in developing countries. On a final note, issues concerning adequate online interaction among the students as well as between them and their teachers pose a significant issue for online learning during the pandemic (Oluwatoyosi, Adebajo & Adewumi 2022).

Secondary Education in Nigeria and in Zamfara state is equally sure to have fair share of the issues and challenges of adopting e-learning on a large scale for the first time. Bello (2021) stressed that there were Federal developed and state developed e-learning packages targeted at teachers and students in Nigerian states. Here, more theoretical postulates, the researchers have strong ground to investigate how adoption of e-learning fared in Zamfara during the period. This is especially as the adoption was used carpeted approach to both theoretically oriented subjects and practically oriented ones. Already researchers in the field of educational technology have stressed that practically oriented subjects do not always easily translate to the online setting (Luliano, Mazzilli, Zambelli, Macaluso, Raviolo, Picerno 2021)

The main theoretical foundation for this study is the technology acceptance model (TAM) grounded in Fishbein and Ajzen's (1975) research on beliefs, attitudes, and behaviours. The theory states that perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use predict attitudes and actual behaviours towards technology adoption. Fundamentally, TAM captures the user's overall attitude toward online technologies include remote teaching. Davis (1993) explains perceived ease of use as the degree to which a person believes that using the system will require minimal effort, whereas perceived usefulness is how well the information system will help them execute their jobs. In essence, it could be argued that secondary school teachers in Zamfara State would embrace the use of e-learning resources for teaching-learning if encouraged and made to see the ease of its use and its usefulness in the performance of their duties as educators who must operate in the Post-COVID-19 period. (Davis, etal 1989; & Shehu, etal, 2021).

The outbreak of Covid-19 led to even greater embracement of e-learning not only at theoretical levels but also at practice levels. Extant literature shows that globally e-learning was experimented to convey educational content at various levels of schooling including secondary. These practices raised new issues and revealed fresh challenges regarding e-learning. A study conducted by Maatuk, Elberkawi, Aljawarneh, Rashaideh & Alharbi (2022) investigated The COVID-19 pandemic and E-learning: challenges and opportunities. The findings revealed the issues of unusually high internet cost, low teachers' and students' preparedness and technical constraints as major challenges. These issues are viewed by many researchers as regurgitation of the e-learning problems of the old. However, further argued that the swift switch to e-learning occasioned by Covid-19 brought about a feeling of distance even though it was initially believed to reduce one. They further elaborated that pre-recorded lectures or slide-based presentations greatly limited student motivation, engagement with the teachers as well as satisfaction. (Bello, 2021; Moustakas & Robrade; 2022).

There are other studies conducted by the proponents supporting the use of e-learning resources for teaching-learning process in this modern age of technological innovativeness despite its associated challenges such as: Stefanovic et al.'s (2011) finding on the significance of interaction among users in the e-learning environment, Sun et al. (2008) had found that perceived interaction among learners was not a significant driver of learner satisfaction in an e-learning environment, even though operationalization of the study variables were similar for both studies. With 295 respondents from Taiwan, Sun et al. (2008) performed stepwise multiple regression to

determine key factors that contribute to learner satisfaction with e-learning systems under two extra dimensions ("design and learner") as compared to that of Stefanovic et al. (2011). Different sample sizes and study locations could be attributable to the varying results. Similarly, some researchers employed, in line with their fundamental framework and in addition to perceived satisfaction for usage in teaching & learning, variables such as interactive intent for future use, communicativeness, structure, quality of information, perceived learning outcome, usefulness, and quality of the system. Contrary to the findings of Stefanovic et al. (2011) and Sun et al. (2008), Damnjanovic et al.'s (2015) study reported no significant influence of online "system and information" quality on perceived satisfaction, and also in opposite sides with Perez-Perez et al. (2020), Damnjanovic et al. (2015) rather found communicativeness as the most important predictor of learner performance in an e-learning environment

Objectives of the study

1. To investigate the extent to which e-learning resources were employed in teaching secondary school students during post COVID-19 in Zamfara State.
2. To examine the success and challenges of using e-learning resources at Post COVID-19 by Zamfara State Secondary School Teachers
3. To suggest ways to improve secondary school bound e-learning resources in post COVID-19 period

Research Questions

1. To what extent do secondary school teachers use e-learning for teaching activities in Zamfara State?
2. What are the success and challenges of using e-learning at Post COVID-19 by Zamfara State Secondary School Teachers?

3. What are the suggested ways to improve on secondary school bound e-learning usage at post COVID-19 period?

METHODOLOGY

To achieve the above, the experiences of some identified secondary school teachers in Zamfara state have been explored through the use of qualitative survey design with open ended questions mimicking interviews. Specifically, attention was given to experiences of teachers regarding the transition to e-learning and attempt to understand the challenges and other issues associated with these experiences. The sampling was purposive Targeting only teachers who actively engaged in e-learning during Covid-19 pandemic in Zamfara state. Additional face-to-face sessions were held with the participants for more in-depth. Three teachers were chosen each from five secondary schools namely: ZACAS staff school Gusau, Muslim foundation secondary school Gusau, Government day secondary school Tsafe, Zamfara state college of arts and science Gusau and school for continuing

RESULTS

Research Question 1:

To what extent do secondary school teachers use e-learning for teaching activities in Zamfara State?

The COVID-19 induced e-learning resources used for teaching activities by Zamfara State Secondary School Teachers.

The responses obtained from participants on teachers' use of e-learning devices revealed that there were arrays of e-learning resources that were used for teaching and learning process by teachers in the selected secondary schools in the state under study and such includes the following:

1. **Video:** Video is an electronic medium for the recording, copying and broadcasting of moving visual images. This method is used by any visual learners or students who learn best by seeing the material rather than hearing or reading about it.

education (women) Gusau. All the respondents are permanent teachers with the schools. Very minimal amount of demographic/background questions were asked according to the need and 9 are male while 6 are female. The instrument was first piloted with a group of teachers twice with an interval of two weeks to ascertain reliability and a reliability of 0.81 was achieved with Pearson moment correlation coefficient. The questions focused on the objectives of the research. The chosen questions reflect prevalent themes obtained in other literature that address issues to do with engagement with e-learning by teachers. Responses were kept anonymous as only codes were given to the respondents and all participants provided informed consent before starting the survey. Thematic analysis was used to analyze the data which include steps such as familiarizing with the data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, and defining themes as well as assigning responses to themes.

Teachers can access video clips through the internet instead of relying on DVDs or VHS tapes. Websites like YouTube are used by many teachers. Teachers can use messaging programs such as Skype, Adobe Connect, or webcams, to interact with guest speakers and other experts. There is an increased retention and better results when video is used in a lesson. . Systematic video development method creation holds promise for creating video models that positively impact student learning. (Hong,2002; Peñarrubia-Lozano, etal.2021; & . Shraim, etal 2010).

2. **Audio:** Any learning done via listening to any material is an audio method of learning. Audio, an electrical or other representation of sound. Digital audio, representation of sound in a form processed and/or stored by computers or other digital electronics. Audio, audible content in media production and publishing. The radio has been around for a long time and has been used in educational classrooms. Recent technologies have allowed classroom teachers to stream audio over the internet. There are also webcasts and podcasts available over the internet for students and teachers to download.
3. **Computers, tablets and mobile devices:** Recent technology has resulted in development of Desktops, laptops, I – pads, Tablets, Macbooks which are been used extensively in market. These devices have been contributed at large extent in learning. Paper is now being replaced by E-learning. Computers and tablets allow students and teachers access to websites and other programs, such as Microsoft Word, PowerPoint, Excel, PDF files, and images. These tools help learners to express their ideas. Excel helps the mathematical working of the study. PowerPoint helps the presentation of the study done by the learner. Graphs, Pie charts, diagrams helps learner to analyse the data studied which helps to give a better result . (Hong,2002; Peñarrubia-Lozano, etal.2021; & . Shraim, etal 2010).
4. **Blogging** A blog (a truncation of the expression web log) is a discussion or informational site published on the World Wide Web and consisting of discrete entries ("posts") typically displayed in reverse chronological order (the most recent post appears first). The blogs can be single user or multiple users. A majority is interactive, allowing visitors to leave comments and even message each other on the blogs, and it is this interactivity that distinguishes them from other static website. Bloggers do not only produce content to post on their blogs, but also build social relations with their readers and other bloggers.
5. **Webcams: Creation of virtual classroom** has been facilitated by these Webcams. A webcam is a video camera that feeds or streams its image in real time to or through a computer or computer network. When "captured" by the computer, the video stream may be saved, viewed or sent on to other networks via systems such as the internet, and email as an attachment. When sent to a remote location, the video stream may be save, viewed or on sent there. Unlike an IP camera (which uses a direct connection using Ethernet or Wi-Fi), a webcam is generally connected by a USB cable, FireWire cable, or similar cable, or built into computer hardware, such as laptops. Webcam helps in establishment of video links, permitting computers to act as videophones or videoconference stations, where the students can learn through this video conferencing. Other popular uses include security surveillance, computer vision, video broadcasting, and for recording social videos. Webcams are known for their low manufacturing cost and flexibility, making them the lowest cost form of video telephony. They have also become a source of security and privacy issues, as some built-in webcams can be remotely activated via spyware. (Hong,2002; Peñarrubia-Lozano, etal.2021; & Shraim, etal 2010).
6. **Screen casting:** A screencast is a digital recording of computer screen output, also known as a video screen capture, often containing audio narration. The term

screencast compares with the related term screenshot; whereas screenshot generates a single picture of a computer screen, a screencast is essentially a movie of the changes over time that a user sees on a computer screen, enhanced with audio narration. Screencasts can help demonstrate and teach. Educators may also use screencasts as another means of integrating technology into the

curriculum. Students can record video and audio as they demonstrate the proper procedure to solve a problem on an interactive whiteboard. This method allows users to share their screens directly from their browser and make the video available online so that the viewers can stream the video directly. (Hong,2002; Peñarrubia-Lozano, etal.2021; & . Shraim, etal 2010).

Research Question 2

What are the prospects and challenges of using e-learning at Post COVID-19 by Zamfara State Secondary School Teachers?

The thematic analysis of respondents' narrations on the prospects of using e-learning during post COVID-19 is summarized as follows:

- i. The used of e-learning resources has made students' learning easier, affordable and convenient thereby enabling them to be active participants in their mode
- ii. E-learning makes student more technology savvy.
- iii. The flexibility & self-paced method of learners tends to democratized learning contents thereby making learners to progress at their own level
- iv. Teachers & students using e-learning resources sees learning as fun and learners centre pedagogical oriented in nature which help to break away from time and space constrained
- v. It goes a long way to provides opportunity for learners to complete their studies any time the student wants and enhanced acquisition of technological skills through practice with tools and computers for teaching-learning process

Furthermore, the interviewees' responses to this question were thematically analyzed. The summary of the analysis is discussed below:

Swift switch to e-learning

One of the emergent theme was the abrupt and sudden migration to e-learning which came to many respondents (in this case teachers) unprepared or ill-prepared. This migration was, of course, due to the unforeseen outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic. Though many institutions in the world and in Nigeria were used to e-learning but the secondary schools in zamfara state and other Nigeria states are witnessing for the first time. The migration however did not last forever as the school have since resumed to normal at the Post-Covid Period, but the e-learning structure and resources remain intact. This led some respondents (respondents) to describe the e-learning as "partial e-learning experimentation". For many teachers, this sudden shift compelled them to embark on e- teaching with little or no preparation. It is also viewed as trial and error situation for many teachers

The challenge of distant interaction

The need for interaction between teachers and students and among teachers themselves was a serious emergent theme as revealed by teachers in e-learning used.. The sense of alienation caused by developing or implementing e-learning away from the normal teaching learning environment seriously affected teachers resolve to teach. This is can be referenced to as revealed in

term of demotivation and dissatisfaction experienced through used. Another observed challenge could be that though lessons may be delivered online but the students may suffer loss of focus and attention unlike in classroom where teacher can call his or her attention immediately. Technical issues prevent many less to do students from accessing the e-learning. Even with physical interaction some students may lag behind as revealed through the respondents. The strength of internet connections many atimes cannot support active real time interaction with the students coupled with insufficient or less data amidst e-learning utilization process.

Darth of resources and technical support

Challenges and issues in e-learning were many. some were pre-existing before the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic but some arose due to the abrupt nature of e-learning experimentation in secondary schools which happened on a broad scale for the first time. Shortage of equipment and limited tools, electricity shortages and outages, cost of internet data have all surfaced as part the issues. Similarly lack of technical support was viewed as discouraging. The respondents generally opine that doing away with these problems will help them, the schools and students improve on e-learning. It was suggested unfettered access to electricity by way of installing solar power as done in some schools. "If there is way teachers can have high quality Android phones that can improve their performance in development and implementation of e-learning. The secondary schools usually suffer from the general problem of no electricity and low **vii.**

Research Question 3

What are the suggested ways to improve on secondary school bound e-learning usage at post COVID-19 period?

reliable internet. Solving this two will make any future e-learning more successful. Similarly, that government websites that teachers are asked to access or direct their students to, need to use simple content so that teachers and students with limited data can access them. Not every teacher has money to buy much data. Need for special training session on how to teach and learn online e-learning will be success. Some of the teachers are already using the internet, they only need to be taught how to use it educationally

Basically, e-learning infrastructure and quality of support system were critical in utilizing the resources for teaching and learning process in secondary school system in the state but the existing facilities are not fully supportive, this is so because, most of the secondary schools in the state were not fully fledged ICT complied as enshrined in the blue-print of the policy on the implementations of ICT in Basic Education. Additionally, the below are other related challenges:

- i.** Quality of content and assessment;
- ii.** Peer support networks;
- iii.** E-learning. quality of the system that includes proper maintenance of software and hardware recourses;
- iv.** Skills gap in the initial training of teachers in e-learning utilizations for instructional process
- v.** Equipment's used are expensive and some of the e-learning resources are not very user friendly, hence the learners' faces difficulty in its uses
- vi.** Students' NOT being fully acquainted with the resources usage for learning, that is the (Swift switch to e-learning)

To answer this question, the interviewees' responses were also analyzed using thematic procedure. Their narrations were summarized and presented as follow:

- i. The state government should ensure that basic education policy on e-learning uses and the procurement & provision of all the required infrastructure needed for quality of content and assessment delivery in school system is put in place for effective and efficiency in instructional purposes
- ii. To ensure e-learning. quality of the system that includes proper maintenance of software and hardware recourses for school system demand for state to called for knowledge expert as an overseer in order to have optimum utilization
- iii. Secondary school teachers identify with skills gap in the initial training process should be given opportunity additional induction training and relevant courses in e-learning utilizations for instructional process
- iv. All required equipment's used in e-learning environment are expensive and some of the e-learning resources are not very user friendly, hence, state government to interface and provided the needed support
- v. Students' already are used to different kind of e-learning resources for other uses but basically NOT being fully acquainted with the resources for learning, hence state should go along way to support its uses for educational purposes through series of workshop, seminar & symposium in order to reduce the friction of (Swift switch to e-learning)

CONCLUSION

This paper looked at Challenges of Using e-learning Resources for Quality

Education Delivery in Post COVID19, a case study of some selected secondary schools in zamfara state from teachers' perspective. The identified challenges related to e-learning utilization as practiced by secondary school teachers in the Post- COVID-19 as identified includes, e-learning infrastructure and quality of support system which are critical in utilizing the resources for teaching and learning process in secondary school system in the state but the existing facilities are not fully supportive, this is so because, most of the secondary schools in the state were not fully fledged ICT complied as enshrined in the blue-print of the policy on the implementations of ICT in Basic Education. Additionally, the subsidiary challenges as: Quality of content and assessment; Peer support networks; E-learning. quality of the system that includes proper maintenance of software and hardware recourses; Skills gap in the initial training of teachers in e-learning utilizations for instructional process; Equipment's used are expensive and some of the e-learning resources are not very user friendly, hence the learners' faces difficulty in its uses; Students' NOT being fully acquainted with the resources usage for learning, that is the (Swift switch to e-learning) were discussed. While, suggested ways of improvement were elaborated upon

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Teachers should be integral part of all future e-learning efforts, especially at the pre-tertiary level where most teachers are in experienced
2. The basic infrastructure such as electricity must be adequately provided
3. ICT infrastructure must be adequately provided to schools and teachers
4. Instilling maintenance culture must be ensued in schools

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